

**STUDIES ON THE CIRCULAR DICHROISM AND ROTATORY DISPERSION,
PART II. ANALYSIS OF THE CURVES OF CIRCULAR DICHROISM
AND ROTATORY DISPERSION OF AMMONIUM VANADYL
D-TARTRATE**

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 278) the author has measured the circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion of ammonium vanadyl *d*-tartrate. The curves of circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion in the region of absorption have been analysed. The circular dichroism can be represented by the equation of Kuhn and Szabo (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, B, 18, 69) which is

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2}$$

where $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ is the maximum circular dichroism corresponding to the frequency ν_0 , the parameter θ is related to the half-width of the band of circular dichroism by the relation ν (half-width) = 1.6652 θ . The rotatory dispersion can be represented by the equation of Kuhn and Braun (*ibid.*, 1930, B, 8, 281) which is

$$[M] = \frac{100}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} \theta} \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta}\right)^2} \int_0^{\nu_0 - \nu} e^{-x^2} dx - \frac{\nu}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

where $[M]$ is the molecular rotatory dispersion for a length of the solution 1 cm. and the other symbols have the same significance as before. The discrepancies between the experimental and theoretical values have been explained and also the merit of the equation of Kuhn and Braun in explaining rotatory dispersion in absorbing media.

A method of preparing ammonium vanadyl *d*-tartrate and of measuring the absorption, circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion in the visible region was given by the author in the previous part (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945 22, 278). In this communication an attempt has been made to explain the results.

From the ellipticity, circular dichroism was calculated by the relation,

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = \frac{4 \log_{10} e \phi}{c.l.}$$

where ϵ_l and ϵ_r are the molecular extinction coefficient for *l* and *r* light; c is the molar concentration, l is the length in centimetre, ϕ is the ellipticity expressed in radians. If ϕ is expressed in degrees, we have

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = \frac{4 \times 0.4343 \times \phi}{0.1 \times 0.5 \times 57.296}$$

These observed values of $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)$ are given in Table I against the respective wave-lengths. The values $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)$ for the first absorption band are then plotted against frequency ν in Fig. 1 to get the experimental curve of circular dichroism. The corresponding graph for the second absorption band is obtained in Fig. 2.

These curves of circular dichroism can be expressed to a very close approximation by means of the equation of Kuhn and Szabo,

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2}$$

$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ is the maximum value of the circular dichroism corresponding to the frequency ν_0 , ν' is the half-width of the band related to θ according to the equation $\nu' = 1.6652 \theta$. This equation represents a curve which is symmetrical with respect to frequencies. The values of ν_0 , ν' and $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$, as obtained from each curve, are set out in Table II. The half-width of the first curve is taken as twice the "semi-half width" as observed on the side of longer wave-length and the half-width of the second curve is similarly taken as twice the "semi-half width" in the shorter wave-length,

FIG. 1.

because the short wave-length side of the first curve and the long wave-length side of the second curve have been influenced one by the other with opposite circular dichroism. The calculated values of $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_r)$ according to the equation above and the corresponding curves of circular dichroism are given side by side in Table I and Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 2.

TABLE I

 Concentration of ammonium vanadyl *d*-tartrate = *M*/10.

l = 5 mm.

First circular dichroism curve.				Second circular dichroism curve.			
λ .	$\nu \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\text{obs.}}$	$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\text{calc.}}$	λ .	$\nu \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\text{obs.}}$	$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\text{calc.}}$
6667Å	4.5	-0.46*	-0.46	5660A	5.3	0.2304	0.4749
6500	4.615	-0.6852	-0.7068	5560	5.395	0.7396	0.7065
6438	4.66	-0.8487	-0.7912	5500	5.454	0.77	0.8726
6240 = λ_0	4.8 = ν_0	-0.92*	-0.92	5494	5.46	0.89*	0.89
6200	4.839	-0.9913	-0.9093	5461	5.493	0.9581	0.9893
6000	4.999	-0.6972	-0.6782	5360	5.597	1.346	1.305
5900	5.084	-0.3759	-0.4944	5300	5.659	1.497	1.464
5893	5.1	-0.46*	-0.46	5200	5.769	1.595	1.696
5780	5.19	-0.1030	-0.2852	5100 = λ_0	5.88 = ν_0	1.78*	1.78
				5000	5.999	1.637	1.684
				4916	6.102	1.534	1.469
				4800	6.25	1	1.04
				4762	6.3	0.89*	0.89

TABLE II

λ_0 in Å.	$\nu_0 \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\text{max.}}$	$\nu' \times 10^{-14}$.	$\theta \times 10^{-14}$.
	(a) Parameters of first circular dichroism curve.			
6240	4.8	-0.92	0.8	0.3604
	(b) Parameters of second circular dichroism curve.			
5100	5.88	1.78	0.84	0.5034

Interpolated

Analysis of the Curve of Rotatory Dispersion

The experimental data for the measurement of rotatory dispersion for *M*/10 concentration of ammonium vanadyl *d*-tartrate and length of the solution 5 mm. have been given in the previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 278). From the observed rotation, molecular rotation [*M*] was calculated by the relation [*M*] = 100 α /*c* where α is the rotation per cm. column of the medium, *c* is the molar concentration. Therefore in this case

$$[M] = \frac{100 \times 2 \times \alpha_{\text{obs}}}{0.1}$$

It is obvious that this [*M*] is the algebraic sum of all the partial rotations due to different optically active absorption bands in the visible, ultraviolet and Schumann region for 1 cm. length of the column of the medium. These observed values of [*M*] are given in Table III and graphically represented against λ in Fig. 3.

An attempt has been made to analyse the curve of rotatory dispersion by means of the equation of Kuhn and Braun.

$$[M] = \frac{100}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\text{max.}}}{\log_{10} e} \cdot \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}} e^{-x^2} dx - \frac{\theta}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

The symbols have the same significance as given before. The molecular partial rotations $[M]_1$ and $[M]_2$ for different wave-lengths for the two optically active absorption bands in the visible region are then calculated from the already determined values ν_0 , θ and $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}$ as given in Table II. In making the calculations use is made of the table of values of the integral

$$e^{-c^2} \int_0^c e^{x^2} dx \left(c = \frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta} \right)$$

for various values of c , as given by Kuhn (Freudenberg, "Stereochemie", Leipzig, 1932, p. 381). A graph was constructed by plotting c against Kuhn's values of the integrals and reading off the values of the integral for those values of c which correspond to the particular frequencies. For values of c greater than 3.2, the value of the integral

$$e^{-c^2} \int_0^c e^{x^2} dx$$

is taken approximately to be equal to $1/2c$.

In Table III are given these calculated partial rotations $[M]_1$ and $[M]_2$ due to the two absorption bands in the visible region and also their algebraic sum. In the last column of the table is given the difference between the total observed rotation and the algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations. This difference evidently represents the residual rotation due to absorption bands in the ultraviolet and Schumann region. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotation and also the residual rotation are plotted in Fig. 3 and the respective curves obtained.

FIG. 3.

TABLE III

λ	[M]	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max} = -0.92 \\ \lambda_0 = 6240 \text{ \AA} \\ \rho = 4.8 \times 10^{16} \\ \theta = 0.3604 \times 10^{14} \end{array} \right.$		$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max} = 1.78 \\ \lambda_0 = 6100 \text{ \AA} \\ \rho = 4.8 \times 10^{16} \\ \theta = 0.5084 \times 10^{14} \end{array} \right.$		$([M]_1 + [M]_2)$	$([M]_1 - [M]_2 + [M]_3)$
		[M] ₁	[M] ₂	[M] ₁	[M] ₂		
6500 $\text{\AA}$	3100	-1376	1031	-345	2445		
6438	2220	-1101	1095	-9	2220		
6240	—	64.3	1352	1416	—		
6200	3580	432.9	1443	1876	1704		
6000	4600	1673	1898	3571	1269		
5900	6000	1987	2191	4179	1822		
5780	0440	2024	2582	4606	1834		
5660	7040	1806	2948	4754	2286		
5560	7040	1903	3141	4744	3296		
5500	6800	1406	3158	4564	2236		
5461	6520	1317	3116	4433	2087		
5360	5520	1119	2735	3654	1666		
5300	4200	1020	2315	3345	655		
5200	2700	910.1	1236	2140	554		
5100	—	820.4	-1418	678.6	—		
5000	360	714.8	-1658	-943	1303		
4916	100	674.8	-2799	-3124	2224		
4600	160 ?	627	-3794	-3167	3327 ?		

DISCUSSION

The study of the circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion of ammonium vanadyl d-tartrate reveals the following characteristic features.

When ammonium vanadate $(\text{NH}_4)\text{VO}_3$ is reduced with hydrobromic acid and the reduced salt is mixed with requisite amount of tartaric acid and neutralised with ammonia, a complex salt having the composition $(\text{NH}_4)_2[(\text{VO})\text{H}_2\text{C}_4\text{O}_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is obtained. The salt is very unstable and undergoes oxidation in presence of air. It has two optically active absorption bands in the visible region. Since circular dichroism cannot occur in a mixture in which the activity and absorption are due to different molecules, so it is evident that a complex is formed between tartaric acid and reduced vanadium salt and the optical activity and absorption are produced by the same molecule. The chromophoric groups which are responsible for the two absorption bands in the visible region and for optical activity due to induced dissymetry are in the course of investigation.

The circular dichroism in these two bands are opposite in sign. The maximum circular dichroism $(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ of the first absorption band occurs at $\lambda_0 = 6240 \text{ \AA}$ and the maximum circular dichroism $(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ of the second absorption band occurs at $\lambda_0 = 5100 \text{ \AA}$. Circular dichroism can be represented approximately by the expression

$$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_u - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2}$$

taking that the curve of circular dichroism is symmetrical with respect to frequencies since circular dichroism of the short wave-length side of the first absorption band is complicated by opposite circular dichroism of the long wave-length side of the second absorption band. There is a better agreement between the experimental value and the theoretical value on the long wave-length side of the first absorption band and the short wave-length side of the second absorption band. The divergence between the theoretical and experimental values on the short wave-length side of the first absorption band and long wave-length side of the second absorption band is due to their mutual influence.

Within the region studied, it is found that the rotation gradually increases in the first absorption band, reaches a maximum on entering the second absorption band and then gradually decreases. The partial rotation due to both the bands in the visible region were calculated both inside the band where it is generated and outside it by the wellknown equation of Kuhn and Braun from the data on the measurement of circular dichroism. The sum of these two partial rotations clearly explains the above observation of the rotatory dispersion within the region studied, for the observed rotation is the algebraic sum of these two partial rotations and residual rotation which in this region may be taken to be normal. The usual characteristics of the anomalous rotatory dispersion associated with the first absorption band do not appear in our measurements as they all lie towards the longer wave-lengths which have not been studied.

The curve of difference in Fig. 3 represents the residual partial rotation due to bands in the ultraviolet and Schumann region, hence should be normal i. e. the rotation should increase progressively with decreasing wave-length but the experimental curve contains two loops one in the first absorption band and the other in the second absorption band. These loops are the conspicuous features of the curve of rotatory dispersion in the region of absorption. Since these loops are not completely eliminated, it indicates that the equation of Kuhn and Braun inadequately represents the partial rotations inside the absorption bands.

Similar observation was made by Lowry and Hudson (*Phil. Trans.*, 1933, A 232. 146) by studying the rotatory dispersion of xanthates and urethanes in the region of absorption.